

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MACON****FIRST NAME: EZECHIEL****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord -Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1. According to the Turabian style guide, what is the primary purpose of citing sources in academic writing?
 - To increase the word count of the paper.
 - To acknowledge the work of other researchers and avoid plagiarism.¹**
 - To make the paper look more professional.
 - To confuse the reader with numerous footnotes.

2. In the Turabian style, what is the main difference between the notes-bibliography style and the author-date style?

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139-146.

- The notes-bibliography style is used for humanities, while the author-date style is preferred in the sciences.²**
- The notes-bibliography style uses parenthetical citations, whereas the author-date style uses footnotes.
- There is no significant difference; it is a matter of preference.
- The author-date style is only used in digital documents.
3. What is a critical component of constructing a solid research argument, according to Turabian?
- Using complex vocabulary to articulate ideas.
- Focusing solely on quantitative data.
- Building the argument around answers to readers' questions and providing evidence.³**
- Ensuring the paper is long enough to cover the topic comprehensively.
4. According to the Turabian guide, how should researchers approach the revision process of their draft?
- Revise only for grammar and spelling mistakes.
- Ensure the argument is coherent and the evidence supports the thesis.⁴**
- Focus on adding more sources to strengthen the argument.

² Ibid., 143.

³ Ibid., 75.

⁴ Ibid., 112.

- Limit revisions to the introduction and conclusion for clarity.
5. What does the Turabian style guide suggest about using quotations in academic writing?
- Quotations should be used sparingly and integrated seamlessly into the text.**⁵
- Most of the paper should use direct quotations to support the thesis.
- Quotations are discouraged; paraphrasing is always preferable.
- Only quotations from primary sources are considered valid.
6. What is the first step in academic essay writing?
- Writing the conclusion.
- Starting the essay.**⁶
- Editing the essay.
- Researching the topic.
7. Which of the following best defines plagiarism?
- Using shared knowledge without citation.
- Paraphrasing with citation.
- Copying someone else's work without giving credit.**⁷
- Citing sources in the bibliography only.

⁵ Ibid., 201.

⁶ EUCLID, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 6-14.

⁷ Ibid., 34.

8. How should “World Health Organization” be abbreviated according to WHO style?

- W.H.O.**⁸
- W H O.
- WHO.
- World Health Org.

9. How should species names be written according to WHO style?

- Both generic and species names are in all caps.
- The generic name is capitalized, and the species name is lowercase.**⁹
- Both names are in lowercase.
- Both names are italicized with initial capitals.

10. According to WHO style, how should dosages be written?

- Write out fractions entirely, even if the quantity is under 10.
- Use Arabic numerals and symbols except for those under 10.
- Spell out numbers under ten and use symbols for 10 and over.**¹⁰
- Always abbreviate units like g and kg after figures.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd ed (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 2-12.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 11.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 26.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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